

THE DISCOURSE ON FORMAL CONTEXTS IN THE SPHERE OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract. *In this article, the use of discourse, its characteristics and types of their use in the official text and speeches are widely studied and analyzed. In particular, linguistic issues such as the use of speech in formal contexts in the field of higher education and its types and characteristics are covered in detail in this scientific work. Also, the wide use of expressions which commonly used in formal speeches are illustrated in this article with the help of several examples.*

Keywords: *language, discourse, context, description, narration, exposition, argumentation.*

Discourse is one of the four systems of language, the others being vocabulary, grammar and phonology. Discourse is generally any form of verbal communication, whether spoken or written. The role of discourse in linguistics is to provide a body of text for various types of analysis. These may include research into grammar, sociolinguistics, psycholinguistics and discourse analysis.

The word discourse is derived from the latin prefix *dis-* meaning “away” and the root word *currere* meaning “to run”. Discourse, therefore, translates to “run away” and refers to the way that conversations flow.

Discourse can refer to any kind of communication and appears in literature (both poetry and prose), speeches, advertisements, diaries, blog posts, definitions and verbal conversations. An example of discourse is when you discuss something with your friends in person or over a chat platform. Discourse can also be when someone expresses their ideas on a particular subject in a formal and orderly way, either verbally or in writing.

The French philosopher Michel Foucault used the term “discourse” to refer to the relationship of communication in real-world power structures. Foucault was more of a social theorist than a linguist; nevertheless, his theories about pragmatics, or how language conveys meaning, has had significant influence on the way many academicians view discourse. As Foucault uses the term, the role of discourse in linguistics is to establish the real-world meaning of statements. He argued that discourse locks people into certain modes of thought and action.

There are traditionally four different types of discourse, namely argument, narration, description, and exposition. Many acts of communicate include more than one of these types in quick succession.

Description is the first type of discourse. Description helps the audience visualize the item or subject by relying on the five senses. Its purpose is to depict and explain the topic by the way things look, sound, taste, feel, and smell. Description helps readers visualize characters, settings, and actions with nouns and adjectives. Description also establishes mood and atmosphere. Examples of the descriptive mode of discourse include the descriptive parts of essays and novels. Description is also frequently used in advertisements.

Narration is the second type of discourse. The aim of narration is to tell a story. A narrator usually gives an account of an event, which usually has a plot. Examples of the narrative mode of

discourse are novels, short stories, and plays. Consider this example from the speech of minister during the meeting with the delegation of Hungary:

“From the history of our relations in the field of higher education, we can mention the meeting at the Ministry on March 23, 2016 with a Hungarian delegation consisting of senior officials of the Ministry of Foreign Economic Relations and Foreign Affairs of Hungary, headed by Deputy Minister Laszlo Szabo. The meeting was also attended by the Ambassador of Hungary to the Republic of Uzbekistan Peter Santo.”

In this case, the minister uses the information about the previous meeting with other delegation from this country. Although this concludes the introduction to the meeting, it does not spoil the participants' view of the end of the meeting. On the contrary, since the information emphasizes the development of bilateral relations, it arouses interest in the participants.

Exposition is the third type of discourse. Exposition is used to convey background information to the audience in a relatively neutral way. In most cases, it doesn't use emotion and it doesn't aim to persuade. Examples of discourse exposure are definitions and comparative analysis. For this type of discourse, we can see the comparison of coverage of youth with higher education from the ministers' speech at the meeting with rector of the University of Singapore:

“Thus, at present, the coverage of young people with higher education has increased compared to 2017 from 9% to 28.1%.”

What is more, exposure serves as an umbrella term for modes such as:

Exemplification (illustration): The speaker or writer uses examples to illustrate their point.

Cause / Effect: The speaker or writer traces reasons (causes) and outcomes (effects).

Comparison / Contrast: The speaker or writer examines the similarities and the differences between two or more items.

Definition: The speaker or writer explains a term, often using examples to emphasise their point.

Problem / Solution: The speaker or writer draws attention to a particular issue (or issues) and offers ways in which it can be resolved (solutions).

Argumentation is the fourth type of discourse. The aim of argumentation is to persuade and convince the audience of an idea or a statement. To achieve this, argumentation relies heavily on evidence and logic. Lectures, essays and public speeches are all examples of the argumentative mode of discourse. Take a look at this example - an excerpt from Ministers speech at the at the 21st meeting of the Intergovernmental Commission on Economic Cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation:

“It should be emphasized that cooperation in the field of higher education between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Russian Federation is built on the basis of a number of agreements signed in different years.”

In his speech, Minister successfully argued that relation with this country in sphere of higher education is widely developed. He rationalised and validated his claim. By quoting the *number of agreements signed in different years*, Minister argued that the cooperation between two states will continue to develop.

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